

Nigerians beyond the Borders

Construction and Sustenance of a National Identity in Diaspora

Wakil Ajibola Asekun

Department of Psychology, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Lagos, Akoka, Lagos, Nigeria

Afolabi Martins Arogundade

Department of General Studies, Lagos State Polytechnic, Ikorodu, Lagos and currently a PhD student in the Department of Political Science, University of Lagos, Nigeria

Abstract

The rate at which Nigerians relocate to foreign countries has been increasing in recent years; most are relocating in pursuit of better economic opportunities. This study attempted to examine Nigerian immigrants' negotiation and sustenance of Nigerian identity as they seek to make a living in their new locations abroad. The study explored the self-identification experience of the mover, before and after relocation, as well as hosts' attitudes to them, in their quest to find meaning as they strive to adjust to living in the diaspora. The study employed the narrative method of data collection and was conducted in Peckam, London, UK, with 20 participants selected through the snowball sampling technique. The study also used a questionnaire to collect data from participants regarding their demographics. The findings revealed that, despite the negativity in the news about the home country, participants expressed a strong self-identification with their home country. How this was made possible was analysed in the paper. In contrast, the results showed that the same could not be said about the children taken out of the country or born in diaspora: their self-identification was with the country of residence, i.e. the United Kingdom (UK). The study also showed that: Nigerians in the diaspora were unfavourably perceived by the host country; those who were perceived to have failed in the struggle to adjust and find meaning in life abroad would perhaps end up in care homes. The study suggested that further studies should be done to verify this claim.

Introduction

About 190 million people live in countries other than the one in which they were born.¹ Although, it has been difficult to obtain accurate figures of Nigerians in the diaspora – because a sizeable number are not documented – it is suggested that about 20 million Nigerians are making a living in Europe and North America.² The Nigerian migrants may have been motivated by the poor economic situation of the country, in the recent time, to travel and strive to excel in diverse economic circumstances in many countries around the world. Although, the migration of people seeking economic opportunities in a foreign land is not new, nor is it peculiar to Nigerians. Man has always moved – even in ancient times – with the need to relocate being necessitated by a number of reasons such as war, poor economy, political or religious persecution and state failure.

The concept of diaspora has been characterised in many past studies in terms of displacement. However, for the purposes of this study, diaspora is referred to as a community of people that is formed through voluntary or involuntary relocation from their place of origin to a new environment. A major theoretical issue is how individuals who changed geographical/social space negotiate and renegotiate identity to become culturally and socially relevant to their new environment. In addition to the reasons why people move, how relocation affects those who move and those who host them, has been the topic of research in psychology and other related disciplines.³ Several past studies have beamed the searchlight on different aspects of the Nigerian diaspora, e.g. Nigerian pro-democracy movements in the diaspora;⁴ remittances by members of the Nigerian diaspora to the home country;⁵ ethnic and old student associations in the diaspora; and the history of the Nigerian diaspora.⁶

One important area, as far as this study is concerned, that is left out of the literature on the Nigerian diaspora is the experience of Nigerians in foreign countries as they struggle to negotiate or maintain their Nigerian identity. Therefore, the focus of the present research is to examine issues related to relocating and the implications that the movement has for identity construction of immigrants, particularly, those who are of Nigerian extraction. Sustaining one's identity as a Nigerian abroad can be a big issue, as many Nigerians who come in contact with a new social environment have to deal with a stigmatised Nigerian identity. Many Nigerian migrants relocated with great expectations, high hopes, lofty aspirations and a dream of living the good life, which they thought they would never have back home, with the dream of a life abroad resulting in people selling personal property to raise money for visas and flight tickets. Some resort to borrowing, while others use their life savings to fund the cost of their travels in the pursuit of their dream of a life in foreign land.

Beyond the cultural shock that the mover experiences, there are a number of psychological and sociological issues that confront the immigrant. For example, the press has reported that Nigerians are perceived negatively by the citizens of their host countries. They have been labelled as fraudsters, drug peddlers, prostitutes, lousy and dishonest – the list of descriptors is endless. Recently, some Nigerians were the victims of xenophobic attack in South Africa, which could be associated with an unfavourable perception of Nigerians. This was, of course, an extreme response that was widely condemned by the government of South Africa, the Nigerian government and others around the world.

Akinrinade and Ogen⁷ traced the development of Nigerian communities in the diaspora to the pre-colonial era, particularly at the time of the Hausa trans-national links that were expressed through the trans-Saharan trade between the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries. They⁸ argued that the migration of many Nigerians to other countries was not necessarily induced by poverty, as claimed by pro-Marxist theorists, but that it could also be attributed to high economic status, high level of education, and access to media and information – factors that led people to believe they could afford to relocate abroad. Moreover, there were Nigerians who migrated to the UK and later to the United States (US) after independence, primarily to obtain a higher education. Some of these migrants remained in these countries, even when the initial intention was to return to Nigeria to occupy the positions left by the departing British colonial administration. Later, the poor economic situation and high unemployment, occasioned by the oil boom of the 1980s, and recently the political instability arising from military interventions in politics in Nigeria, further exacerbated the inclination to migrate.

Table1: The number of Nigerians in selected countries of Europe and North America⁹

Countries	India	Ireland	Japan	Netherlands	Australia	Canada	UK	USA
Population	9 500	16 300	5 018	9 453	4 519	19 520	174 000	227 000

Source: Cybriwsky (2011)¹⁰; Odafe (2011)¹¹; Office for National Statistics (2011)¹²; Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Nigeria (2009)¹³.

Objectives

- To examine Nigerians' self-identification while they are outside her border
- To ascertain how the Nigerian identity is perceived by non-Nigerians outside Nigeria
- To understand how the Nigerian identity perceived by the hosts affect how Nigerians are treated
- To examine how Nigerians in the diaspora negotiate and sustain their national identity

The research questions are:

- Is there a Nigerian identity in the diaspora?
- What is the process involved in identity sustenance of a person in diaspora?
- How do the hosts perceive Nigerians in diaspora and how does this affect interpersonal interactions between the host and the immigrants?
- How do Nigerians in the diaspora negotiate and sustain their national identity?

Literature Review

Leaving one's country of origin to live in a foreign country can bring about a number of self-changes in a person. An immigrant who visits another country as a tourist, a student or a worker has to adjust to the behaviour expected by the host, through a process of identity negotiation. Martin¹⁴ extended this view by stating that the negotiation could be somewhat difficult, because the movers have to deal with existing social categorisations, which is often characterised by a stigmatised social representation of poverty and crime, especially if the immigrant comes from a less developed country. Construction and sustaining of identity for a foreigner is indeed complex, because most movers strive to maintain contact and identification with the homeland.¹⁵ This is the reason Laguerre, cited by Gibau,¹⁶ identified two kinds of diaspora: 'active diaspora', i.e. those who maintain connections with the homeland; and 'passive diaspora', i.e. those who only maintain symbolic ties. Scholars have also called attention to recent developments that have changed the concept of diaspora. Such developments include the globalisation of markets, improvements in information communication technology, and ease of air transportation. 'Diaspora must now be understood in relation to the local and global phenomenon, whereby the 'here' and the 'there' are no longer mutually exclusive, but are in a constant dialogue.'¹⁷ These dynamic realities have also resulted in some complexity in the way a diasporic identity is understood. Some studies also point to the dilemma of people in the diaspora in terms of raising children born in the diaspora. Do such children develop the identity of the resident's country or the identity of their native country? Kardinaki¹⁸ noted that the impact of relocation on identity formation is shown to persist through generations.

Over the years, researchers have developed a deep interest in the concept of identity and have thus offered many ideas and divergent views that have also compounded the conceptualisation of the construct. Mead used the concept of identity to refer to self.¹⁹ He proposed that the self is developed through meaningful contacts with the environment. He opined that communication is a critical determinant of identity construction, i.e. identity is negotiated and re-negotiated through dialogue. He argued further that 'the self' evolves in terms of an individual's social interaction, and this process continues throughout the life of the human being. The cognitive school of psychology sees identity as the self-categorisation of one's own personal qualities;²⁰ while neo-behaviourists believe that identity is a mechanism of personal development and a way to develop new forms of behaviour and new roles.²¹ Erikson opines that identity is a sense of sameness between the self and somebody else, i.e. the matching of one's self against others. He believed that the identification process requires certain emotional experiences and its functionality includes: integration of one's self into a group; personality development; and regulation of a person's behaviour. It is also an instrument of socialisation, whereby an individual makes the effort to feel, think and behave like others; take on roles; identify with the attributes of another meaningful personality.²² Social identification is also understood as the process of adjusting one's self to the requirements of a social group, and establishing likeness or a match with other members of this social group, and that it is also a way of establishing likeness with some and differences from others.²³

Complexities of National Identity Construction in Nigeria

Nigeria is a highly diverse country of over 250 ethnic nationalities. Before her amalgamation in 1914, she had been ruled by Britain as a southern and a northern protectorate through an indirect rule policy. She got her independence in 1960, which was celebrated with pomp and pageantry as her citizens looked to the future with hope and enthusiasm. At this time, constructing a national identity was not difficult, because all the conditions identified by Smith²⁴ as being necessary for the formation of national identity were clearly present, e.g. a historic territory; common myths; history memories and values; a common public culture; common legal rights and duties; and a common economy with territorial mobility. However, a lot has changed between then and now. Positive effects for out-groups among many ethnic groups in Nigeria appear to have given way to mistrust and suspicion, which is a consequence of perceived unfair distribution of the nation's resources among the federating states of the country.²⁵ This challenge has led to bitter ethnic rivalries and conflicts which snowballed into a civil war between 1967 and 1970. Over and over again, the Nigerian state has made efforts to integrate all ethnic nationalities, through agencies such as Mass Mobilisation and Rural Development in 1984, the National Orientation Agency, the National Youth Service Corp, etc. The success of such efforts is yet to be seen. This is because some people in the country are still agitating for self-determination, especially in South-Eastern Nigeria. There are also conflicts arising from Islamic militancy, which has its root in identification with violent Islamic ideology in the north, and the fight for resource control in the Niger Delta region of the country. These developments underscore the submission of Deaux et al.²⁶ that 'people have the choice to identify with a whole range of different groups (e.g. a city, a region, a country)'. Hence, it seems plausible that the degree to which people will self-identify as a member of a particular group is (at least in part) the outcome of a choice process (i.e. 'Do I wish to identify myself with this particular group?').

Constructing the Nigerian National Identity: Socio-cultural Theory as a Framework

'The English landscape evokes Englishness.'²⁷ Does the Nigerian landscape and the uniqueness of her socio-cultural context confer a sense of sameness to Nigerians? Do Nigerian citizens see themselves as a group? Like other nationalities, Nigerians can be said to have a distinct national identity. The concept of national identity implies a consensus about shared characteristics among groups and a host of local loyalties, e.g. family, work, religion and language. The concept could also be described as the tendency for a people to differentiate themselves from others. It includes: 'an awareness of difference'; a feeling and recognition of 'us' and 'them',²⁸ but also the recognition of sameness in terms of territory, cultural legacy or the state, and the feeling of belonging and allegiance to that which defines or distinguishes one national identity from others or against the expanded definition of identity in the global society. As stated earlier, Smith²⁹ mentioned public culture as one of the determinants of national identity. The elements of public culture that serve as symbolic ties are: music, dress, food, dance, etc. These are some of the symbolic resources from

which an identity emerges.³⁰ This viewpoint has its root in the Vytgoskian (socio-cultural) approach to identity, which is a major theoretical guide for this study. According to Vytgosky,³¹ cultural elements are made up of semiotic units (signs and symbols) that convey meaning about the social origin of a people. Groups employ semiotic devices in their construction of meaning. This they do in their thoughts and in their feelings, as well as in their action. They thus serve as a resource that facilitates the construction and reconstruction of new meanings.³² The semiotic devices have also been found to facilitate transition into parenthood,³³ and the formation and negotiation of professional identity among teachers.³⁴ Zittoun³⁵ also demonstrated how these symbolic resources were used for mediating the relationship with one's self and one's inner feelings, adjusting with social others, and modifying social relationships.

In their descriptive study, Akinrinade and Ogen³⁵ observed that the Nigerian diaspora was as 'disorganised' as the Nigerian state, and that Nigerians could be found in proliferated groups along ethnic lines, such as Igbo, Ijaw, Yoruba, Edo, Hausa and Ibibo. COMPAS³⁶ also mentioned sub-ethnic and hometown associations like the Ikaile World Congress in the US; the London based Odoziobodo Club of Ogwashi-Uku and the Zumunta Association, USA, among others. They reported that ethnic, sub-ethnic and home place associations were critical to the integration of new migrants into the Nigerian diaspora network. Moreover, faith-based associations also played an important role in the integration process. Akinrinade and Ajibewa³⁷ noted that religion was also instrumental as a means of bringing people who share the same religious belief together to fellowship and form a bond. Religious venues are places where people in the diaspora make social connections and cement social relationships. This phenomenon has gained the attention of scholars and researchers in recent times, and findings from such studies show that these religious groups play both a social role and help Nigerians in the diaspora meet their spiritual, cultural and, sometimes, their material needs.³⁸ Thus, as Nigerians in the diaspora came together as a political group, in faith-based association, or ethnic association, these groupings made possible the integration of the Nigerian migrant communities in the host countries. This confirms the assumption of this paper that identity construction and sustenance is achieved through interaction in the social space.

Method

The narrative method of data collection was adopted in this research, in order to study the personal experiences of the participants. A questionnaire was also administered to collect data on participant demographics. Questions included enquired about age, length of stay in the UK, employment status, marital status, etc. The study was carried out in Peckham, UK. This part of England was chosen for the study, because it is an area in the UK where many Nigerian immigrants reside. A total of 20 people were purposely selected for participation in the study. On obtaining the consent of a prospective respondent, the researcher scheduled a mutually agreed date and venue where the conversation was to take place. The study was done in summer; hence it was possible to engage with the participants in a park in the residential area of the respondent. Ten of the 20 participants were Nigerians who had been residing in the country for not less than ten years, while the remaining 10 were Nigerians who had spent not more than one year in the country. This was to enable the

study to obtain a well-balanced view from new and old diaspora Nigerians. Furthermore, selection of the sample was done using the snowball sampling method, i.e. selection of a few participants by the researcher, and asking them to help them to propose other participants who might be willing to participate in the study. The narrative method was considered appropriate for the study, as it is the most suitable method for the study of identity,³⁹ because people come to a realisation of who they really are through the stories they share about their life struggles at specific points in time.⁴⁰ After obtaining the consent of the participants, the conversation with each respondent was tape-recorded and all the data were transcribed verbatim. Heeding the advice of Miles and Huberman⁴¹ on the need to code the experiences of respondents revealed in the conversations, the preliminary analysis was to code these narrated experiences, based on Denzin's conventions of narrative expressions of life experiences.⁴² Among these conventions are family beginnings, reasons for relocation and turning point experiences while in the UK. At the end, the analysis generated was summarised to create a general impression of key factors influencing identity formation, sustenance and/or re-negotiation among Nigerians in the diaspora.

Results

Constructing and Sustaining the Nigerian Identity

Most of the respondents were of the view that they had an already formed national identity from back home before coming to Britain, which they were proud of, despite Nigeria's many problems. This implies that Nigerians in the diaspora keep their Nigerian identity. However, they unanimously admitted the influences of the new environment, the social milieu, the new cultural realities and social circumstances as threats to keeping their Nigerian identity. They therefore reported how they had devised means by which they keep in touch with 'home', thereby helping them to maintain their identity as Nigerians. The means frequently cited in the conversations included the following: Nollywood movies (Nigerian homemade dramas, films, etc.), town association meetings, Nigerian music and dress and other cultural elements.

Usman says:

When you find yourself in a multi-cultural society like UK, you will come in contact with people of diverse backgrounds. Thus, your identity is at a risk of becoming lost; for me, I refuse to let that happen to me. Everywhere I go, I don't hide my identity as a Nigerian. I believe that I am a typical Nigerian, because I still speak Nigerian language, eat Nigerian food, attend Nigerian social events, etc.

In Ade's conversation, he opined:

When you come to live in a very civilised country like Britain, you are constantly face with a strong urge to jettison your cultural traits that you came here with, but you know, home is home no matter what. I strive to keep in touch with home in every possible way, through wearing Nigerian dresses as

often as I can, eating Nigerian foods, dancing to Nigerian music, endeavouring to always speak my language with other Nigerians. Here, these practices have made me to still feel Nigerian.

These sustenance means identified by the research participant are the symbolic resources, which the proponents of Vygotskian tradition had identified as essential tools for identity construction and reconstruction and/or maintenance. The explanation here is that these symbolic resources mediate between people and the mind. This is also consistent with the findings of Hear, Pieke and Vertovec,⁴³ who noted that Nigerians living in the UK draw on diverse social platforms, including national or state level interest groups, like business forum, associations of particular tribal groups, while others are based on gender, religion, political and cultural activities. Hear et al.⁴⁴ also reported that beyond such particular interest groups, Nigerians in the UK are active participants in pan-African diaspora development organisations, such as the London-based NGO, African Foundation for Development (AFFORD).

Moreover, the experiences shared by the participants go a long way in confirming that identity construction is not only a consequence of particular struggles, but also the result of a process in which individuals develop the narratives of their everyday lives – narratives that are contextualised by the ways in which individuals interact with social institutions. These narratives have less to do with the significance of specific institutions and events than they have to do with the ability of certain stories to make sense of the individuals' lives. 'Diasporic identity, thus, is constructed from narratives stemming from a sequence of life events, and while different narratives can be told from the same events, the salience of a given identity depends on which narrative is told.'⁴⁵

One Family, Multiple National Identities

Most of the respondents did not believe that Nigerians born in the UK were developing a Nigerian identity. They thought that, as parents, they were helpless to make their children, who were born in the UK or brought to the UK early, develop a Nigerian identity, even though this was their wish. They pointed out that the frustration of not being able to make their children form a Nigerian identity had compelled some of them to send their children back to Nigeria for their schooling, on the assumption that living among their brothers and sisters in Nigeria would make this possible.

One of the things that baffle me here is the level of freedom that is given to children. I'm of the view that the freedom given them is too much; it is a nightmare to us how children here are indulged. This makes it difficult for us to discipline our kids and make them imbibe our culture. Moreover, the kids don't like to hear about Nigerian culture; they quickly call your attention to the plight of children on Nigerian streets who beg for alms, hawk goods or in the IDP's camp because of Boko Haram. This is because these are some of the negative things the British electronic media show us here. They hardly show something positive for our kids to watch from Nigeria or Africa at large. So they hardly listen to us on anything about Nigeria.

Narratives such as this underscore the fact that identity construction is achieved through interaction in social space. Social space is an array of possible relations that one person can have with others.⁴⁵ Some of these relations are conferred by existing social structures and categorisations and some are chosen or created by the individual. A set of practices (traditions) convey possibilities within social space, although this approach argues that identity is conceived as a form of action that is, first and foremost, rhetorical;⁴⁶i.e. concerned with persuading others (and one's self) about who one is and what one values. These parents acknowledge their efforts in this regard, i.e. persuading their kids to construct the Nigerian identity, which also shows (as Olson et al. stated) that 'identities are not inheritances or preservations, but are, rather, on-going active constructions that emerge out of interactions among groups within socio-political and institutional contexts'.⁴⁷ Even though they feel pained that they were not as successful as they wish, it nonetheless aligns with sociocultural presumptions of identity construction that it is firstly dialogical and discursive, as well as sociocultural in nature.

'Con Men from Africa'

Seventy per cent of the interviewees discussed being perceived negatively by their hosts (white British nationals). They believed that they were being stigmatised by their hosts as people with a con-artist character, and as being fraudulent, corrupt and unable to manage their rich natural resources honestly, and who are now in the UK wanting to take their jobs or defraud them. It was believed by the interviewees that this was the reason why whites did not trust Nigerians with good jobs but gave them their dirty jobs. For example, Chidi (pseudonym) said:

People here have negative perception about Nigerians. They describe Nigeria with negative terms, which is never a true reflection of who we really are. That is worrisome to me, and we are not being helped by the information that Nigerian senior officials give to the outside world. Imagine our president describing us as fraudsters and corrupt! What do you expect others to think of you? After all, it is what you call your dog that other people would call it for you.

Similarly, Dele expressed a sense of indignation with the way the British sometimes looked at him or talked to him, because he is a Nigerian. He believes that he is perceived and treated negatively because of some Nigerians who have engaged in unwholesome behaviour in the past.

Our hosts here think of Nigerians as fraudsters. This is very wrong and prejudicial. I think this perception is due to the experience they may have had from a few people from us. We are stigmatised and labelled as dishonest people, because of these few bad elements. I find these very worrisome. I came here because I was jobless. Nigeria as a country has really not been good to me; that is why I am here.

Experiences of stigmatisation have been further compounded by the low tolerance of the British authorities regarding illegal immigration: there has been much effort by the British authority to limit entry into the country by immigrants who only come to the country in search of job opportunities.

There was a time when there were suggestions in one of the national dailies for people to come up with negative descriptions about what jobs foreigners were doing in the UK. Phrases such as ‘Come here and clean our loo’ were some of the descriptors on the posters of the campaign. These were intended to discourage job seekers from coming to Britain and this kind of practice, as well as others, could reinforce stereotypes about Nigerians and other nationals from Europe residing in UK. More so, the issue of labelling people arose, because migrants are seen as a threat to the national identity of the countries in which they seek work.⁴⁸ The people of Great Britain have expressed disgust (at different times) about the perceived threat of losing their own national identity due to the influx of migrants – not only from Africa, but from Asia and even from Eastern Europe. This fear may have contributed to the motivation for the call for a referendum on whether or not Britain should remain a member of European Union. The referendum’s result – popularly dubbed Brexit – shocked the rest of the world, as the people of Britain voted ‘leave’ on 23 of June 2016. Also, it is a regular practice for British Immigration to deport illegal immigrants to their countries when they find them out.

Collectivistic Oriented, Individualistic context

The narratives of the majority of participants depict a ‘self’ that is collectivistic in orientation, yet located in an individualistic culture. The notion of being ‘my brother’s keeper’ was profoundly observed in the conversations with the participants, whereas they interface with a totally different culture that is largely individualistic in nature: the ‘mind your own business only’ tendency among the white British. Some of the collectivistic tendencies manifest in their regular financial support to their siblings, taking in relations to live with them if there is a need, spending time with one another, visiting and exchanging gifts; but they were of the view that bearing one another’s burden was not a British way of life, therefore, they thought that living with this contradiction was a herculean task in the process of identity sustenance. They believed that those who failed to cope with these realities were lonely, frustrated and depressed, and have developed certain complicated psychological or health problems. For example, Jaye said:

Here you live in a very quiet, ‘mind your own business’ neighbourhood. Many who leave their families behind in Nigeria to hustle here do find themselves lonely often. I believe this has made some of our people here to develop psychological problems. I know not a few Nigerian who have been taken to homes as inmates, because they suffered a nervous breakdown caused by loneliness and depression. Some of us refuse to allow this to happen to us, because we strive to keep in touch with our fellow Nigerians, both here and back at home.

Similarly, Aisha said:

It looks to me the only thing we do here is work, and work – of course mostly at menial jobs we can never be proud of. Besides, not many Nigerians can afford to live in London or other major cities in the UK. Some of my friends who are Nigerians live in secluded areas where they are cut off from others.

Discussion and Conclusion

Kadianaki wondered if moving to a new environment poses a threat to one's national identity (of origin). The experience narrated by the participants in the study did not suggest such a reality: the respondents represented nationality as something irrevocable, which was allowed by providence and ought to be jealously protected. They demonstrated loyalty to their nation of origin and thus chose to sustain their national identity through reliance on certain symbolic elements. This finding is in agreement with the proposition of Weiner, who attempted to distinguish diasporas from migrant communities. He pointed out that the latter group maintains a myth or collective memory of their homeland and see their ancestral homeland as their true home, to which they will eventually return; while the former does not. Weiner's proposition was largely influenced by the Jewish diaspora experience.⁴⁹

The findings of this study reveal the increasing growth of what Soyinka described as ultra-nationalism, which causes the host to perceive immigrants negatively. This phenomenon is now making living abroad more complex: as we write this paper, one of the major issues in the US general election campaign is how to deal with immigrants. Many diasporans continue to complain of unfavourable treatment from their hosts, which is arising from a new wave of ultra-nationalism. It is also suspected to be the cause of Euroscepticism, as Soyinka stated below:

What is happening in Europe shouldn't surprise any of us ... It has happened before. We were here when Enoch Powell was leading his thugs to drive blacks from here ... it's a constant fight to try to get a nation to recognise its own noble persuasions, its own persuasions of the loftiness of human possibility. It's for young people like you to say no to them whenever that happens.⁵⁰

The findings of this study also revealed a scenario of having one family with multiple national identities: parents from Nigeria struggled to sustain their Nigerian identity, while their children aim to construct the British identity. This scenario has implications for the family relationships of Nigerians in the diaspora. According to Berry,⁵¹ the dynamic is not given its deserved prominence in literature. This is because in most cases, immigrants from less developed countries portray themselves, especially to people back home, as making stable, context-independent choices between cultural maintenance and contact with new others. While this repositioning of the self appears as a choice made between nationalities, it is also the case that relocation brings about new self positions. The findings of the study reveal that movement to a new environment not only poses a challenge in making choices between identity categories, but can also create opportunities for self-change that would not have been possible if there was no relocation in the first instance. Immigration does not constrain a stable identity, but can enable creative transformation arising from diversification.

Migrating to wealthier countries has implications for identity-related processes. One way in which this occurs is the loss of one's familiar social context and embracing a totally new environment. The new context that immigrants move into is characterised by different social representations, e.g. the one which the host confers, based on the stereotypes of their nationalities and the general representations these confer on people who generally relocate. Immigrants, therefore, have

to cope with these representations, as well as the expectations of the people in the home country, who think that relocating automatically confers wealth and prestige to movers; and the movers also think that they should not lose the 'self', despite exposure to their new world. Immigrants thus tend to conceal their struggles and pains in their quest to become fulfilled individuals, especially if they found that many people they left back at home are living even a more comfortable life than them who relocated. They tend to show off the 'self' that has progressed in a more civilised world and which also is in touch with home. In their daily lives, immigrants also feel a strong need to be perceived as well adjusted international fellows devoid of the stigma of fraud, indiscipline, or being an economic refugee or corrupt. This study finds that this can be too much of a burden for many Nigerians to bear at the same time; hence, many become disillusioned and may develop psychological problems, which this study hopes can be explored by future studies.

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